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ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА ВЫБОР МЕТОДА УШИВАНИЯ МАТКИ ПРИ КЕСАРЕВОМ СЕЧЕНИИ: АНАЛИЗ АНАМНЕСТИЧЕСКИХ ДАННЫХ.....	76
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THE ROLE OF ANTITIPOXANS IN CORRECTING ACID BASE STATE IN THE BLOOD IN INFANTS BORN WITH CHRONIC HYPOXIA

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ANNOTATION

The primary cause of hypoxic-ischemic brain injury is widely recognized as the restriction of both oxygen supply and essential oxidative substrates necessary for cellular function. This understanding is supported by existing research ([3,4]). The most critical damage to brain cells occurs 2-6-48 hours after birth due to oxidative stress. This process is triggered by the resumption of blood flow to the brain following a period of oxygen deprivation (perfusion deficit). The reintroduction of highly oxygenated blood leads to an overproduction of harmful free radicals, contributing to cell damage.

A study involving 60 premature infants who experienced asphyxia during birth was conducted at the Samarkand Regional Perinatal Centre and the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit of the Samarkand Multidisciplinary Children's Research Medical Centre. These infants were closely monitored to observe the effects of oxidative stress on brain tissue.

Key words: asphyxia, newborns, cerebroprotector, Cytoflavin

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SURUNKALI GIPOKSIYA BILAN TUG'ILGAN CHAQALOQLARDA QONDAGI KISLOTA ASOSINI TUZATISHDA ANTITIPOKXANLARNING ROLI

ANNOTATSIYA

Gipoksik-ishemik miya shikastlanishining asosiy sababi kislorod ta'minotining cheklanishi va hujayra funktsiyasi uchun zarur bo'lgan muhim oksidlovchi substratlar sifatida keng e'tirof etilgan. Ushbu tushuncha mavjud tadqiqotlar ([3,4]) tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanadi. Miya hujayralariga eng jiddiy zarar oksidlovchi stress tufayli tug'ilgandan keyin 2-6-48 soat o'tgach sodir bo'ladi. Bu jarayon kislorod etishmasligi (perfuziya etishmovchiligi) davridan keyin miyaga qon oqimining qayta tiklanishi bilan boshlanadi. Yuqori kislorodli qonning qayta kiritilishi zararli erkin radikallarning haddan tashqari ko'payishiga olib keladi va hujayra shikastlanishiga yordam beradi.

Samarqand viloyati perinatal markazi va Samarqand ko'p tarmoqli bolalar ilmiy-tadqiqot tibbiyot markazining neonatal intensiv terapiya bo'limida tug'ilish vaqtida asfiksiyani boshdan kechirgan 60 nafar erta tug'ilgan chaqaloqlar ishtirokida o'tkazilgan tadqiqot o'tkazildi. Ushbu chaqaloqlar oksidlovchi stressning miya to'qimalariga ta'sirini kuzatish uchun diqqat bilan kuzatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: asfiksiya, yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlar, serebroprotektor, sitoflavin

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РОЛЬ АНТИТИПОКСАНОВ В КОРРЕКЦИИ КИСЛОТНО-ОСНОВНОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ КРОВИ У НОВОРОЖДЕННЫХ, РОДИВШИХСЯ С ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ ГИПОКСИЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Основной причиной гипоксически-ишемического повреждения головного мозга широко признается ограничение поступления кислорода и основных окислительных субстратов, необходимых для функционирования клеток. Это понимание подтверждается существующими исследованиями ([3,4]). Наиболее критическое повреждение клеток мозга происходит через 2-6-48 часов после рождения в результате окислительного стресса. Этот процесс запускается при возобновлении притока крови к мозгу после периода кислородного голодания (дефицита перфузии). Возобновление притока крови с высоким содержанием кислорода приводит к перепроизводству вредных свободных радикалов, способствующих повреждению клеток.

В Самаркандском областном перинатальном центре и отделении интенсивной терапии новорожденных Самаркандского многопрофильного детского научного медицинского центра было проведено исследование с участием 60 недоношенных детей, перенесших асфиксию при рождении. За этими младенцами велось тщательное наблюдение с целью выявления влияния окислительного стресса на ткани головного мозга.

Ключевые слова: асфиксия, новорожденные, церебропротектор, цитофлавин

Relevance of the study. Hypoxia, a deprivation of oxygen supply to the brain, poses a significant threat to newborns. Often originating before birth, this condition frequently persists during labor, contributing substantially to perinatal mortality. Studies indicate that hypoxia and asphyxia are responsible for 20-50% of perinatal deaths, 59% of stillbirths, and are a primary cause of fetal demise in labor or the immediate postnatal period in 72.4% of cases.

Metabolic acidosis is a common complication observed in newborns during the initial hours and days following shock. This condition results in diminished blood flow and volume due to weakened heart muscle function. Furthermore, it reduces the cardiovascular system's responsiveness to medications designed to improve heart function and blood pressure. Metabolic acidosis also leads to a decrease in overall blood vessel resistance, impairing microcirculation. This can result in rapid breathing (tachypnea) and elevated pulmonary pressure. Additionally, constriction of arterioles occurs in the gastrointestinal tract and kidneys, leading to impaired intestinal function, reduced urine output, high potassium levels (hyperkalemia), and increased intracellular sodium levels.

When pneumocyte II activity diminishes due to acidosis, surfactant production declines. This reduction increases the susceptibility to seizure syndrome and shifts the oxyhemoglobin dissociation curve to the right, thereby lowering the affinity of hemoglobin for oxygen. Consequently, cerebral circulation is compromised, leading to intraventricular hemorrhages. It's crucial to recognize that central nervous system injuries sustained during the perinatal period can contribute to early neuropsychiatric disabilities. In fact, 60-70% of cases exhibit signs of early childhood disability.

Metabolic acidosis in a laboratory setting is characterized by a base deficit, measured as Base Excess (BE). BE quantifies the imbalance between bases and acids in the body. It represents the amount of strong base or acid required to restore the pH to its normal level (at a partial pressure of carbon dioxide of 40 mmHg and a temperature of 37°C). A positive BE signifies a depletion of non-carboxylic acids and a corresponding loss of hydrogen ions, while a negative BE indicates an excess of non-carboxylic acids and an increase in hydrogen ions. This measurement is expressed in millimoles per liter (mmol/L), with the normal range being between -2.0 mmol/L and +2.0 mmol/L. Therefore, a negative BE value indicates either a base deficiency or an acid excess, whereas a positive BE value suggests a base excess or an acid deficiency.

Succinic acid plays a crucial role in supporting an organism's metabolic functions through oxidation. Studies involving intravenous administration of succinic acid as part of cytoflavin have demonstrated its direct impact on cellular metabolism and oxygen transportation within tissues [10].

In conditions of low oxygen availability (hypoxia), succinate exhibits significant advantages over other respiratory substrates due to increased oxidation rates and endogenous succinate production. Its influence extends to tissue and cell metabolism, affecting protein synthesis, ion transport, and cellular respiration [10].

Research has established that cytoflavin demonstrates neuroprotective and cerebroprotective properties in treating children with central nervous system (CNS) lesions resulting from hypoxia-ischemia or hypoxia-hemorrhage. Additionally, studies have shown its cardioprotective effects. These findings support the use of cytoflavin as part of a comprehensive treatment approach for newborns in their first

days of life who have neurometabolic disorders related to perinatal injuries [11; 12].

Cytoflavin has been proven to offer protection to both the brain and nervous system in children experiencing damage from oxygen deprivation, whether caused by restricted blood flow or bleeding. Furthermore, studies indicate that cytoflavin also exhibits protective effects on the heart. These findings suggest that cytoflavin could be a valuable component of a multifaceted treatment plan for newborns suffering from neurometabolic disorders stemming from birth-related injuries.

Drug metabolites and intracellular energy metabolism regulators show potential as antihypoxants (agents that combat oxygen deficiency). Cytoflavin, a drug meeting these criteria, presents a cost-effective treatment option for neonates in intensive care settings. Its formulation includes sodium succinate, inosine, riboflavin, and nicotinamide. These components work synergistically to correct intracellular energy metabolism imbalances both during hypoxic-ischemic events and the subsequent reperfusion period, which is characterized by increased free radical activity. While Cytoflavin's components are listed in Uzbekistan's national drug formulary (Order No. 273, November 30, 2021), published research on its use in newborns with asphyxia within Uzbekistan remains unavailable.

The aim. This study investigated the effectiveness of Cytoflavin in treating patients. The research found that there is a limited timeframe, referred to as the "therapeutic window," during which treatment with Cytoflavin can be beneficial following oxygen deprivation and reduced blood flow to the brain. This window extends from two to 48 hours after the initial injury.

Material and methods of research. This study examined 120 preterm infants admitted with a history of birth asphyxia. All patients received care at the Samarkand Regional Perinatal Centre and the neonatal intensive care unit of the Samarkand Multidisciplinary Children's Research Medical Centre. Infants were categorized into three groups based on their gestational age and weight: low birth weight, normal birth weight, and high birth weight. Each group was further subdivided into two subgroups based on asphyxia severity: moderate and severe. Asphyxia diagnosis and severity classification adhered to World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines.

Our clinical observations identified several key factors leading to the prescription of this treatment:

1. A history of complicated pregnancies and deliveries in the mother.
2. Significant oxygen deprivation experienced by the newborn infant.
3. Severe imbalance of acids and bases in the newborn's body at birth.
4. Reduced blood flow to the brain.

In this study, newborns experiencing severe asphyxia were divided into two groups: a treatment group and a control group.

The treatment group received Cytoflavin in addition to standard medical care, while the control group received only standard care. Both groups were carefully matched based on clinical presentation, laboratory results, and severity of asphyxia to ensure comparability. Assessments were conducted on the first day of life and again on the third day to evaluate the effectiveness of Cytoflavin treatment (see Table for detailed findings).

Results of the study

Table 1

The administration of Cytoflavin has been shown to improve markers of hypoxia (oxygen deficiency)

Indicators	Group I (complex treatment + cytoflavin)		Group II (complex treatment)	
	Day 1	Day 3	Day 1	Day 3
pH	7,12 ± 0,02*	7,28 ± 0,01*	7,12 ± 0,02	7,20 ± 0,01
G	0,05	0,02	0,05	0,03

PaCO2 N 30,3 G	36,85 ± 1,20 *	30,18 ± 0,29 *	37,86 ± 1,12	36,24 ± 1,07
PaO2 N 50-80 G	35,82 ± 3,32*	77,8 ± 3,39*	33,21 ± 3,33	56,9 ± 2,15
HCO3 N 21-25 G	16,69 ± 0,34*	22,66 ± 0,54*	16,82 ± 0,36	19,34 ± 0,5
BE N 3,26 (-5,5) G	-14,93 ± 0,69	-7,68 ± 0,74*	-15,34 ± 0,68	-12,33 ± 0,77
SaO2 N>88% G	66,8 ± 2,68*	88, ± 0,58*	65,60 ± 1,89	85,88± 0,39
	8,66	2,07	6,18	1,51

Note: * - degree of reliability $P < 0.05$ compared to group II. The level of significance (P) in testing statistical hypotheses was taken as 0.05.

In newborns undergoing intensive treatment for severe asphyxia and receiving Cytoflavin, a statistically significant improvement in blood acid-base balance (ABC) parameters was observed. The compensation of acidosis (excess acidity in the blood) was more pronounced on day three of life in the group receiving Cytoflavin compared to the control group, where acidosis remained significantly elevated. This persistent acidosis, coupled with other markers of base deficit, raises concerns about the prognosis for the newborns in the control group.

The provided data supports the conclusion that Cytoflavin, when used in conjunction with other therapies for severe neonatal asphyxia, works by addressing specific metabolic imbalances associated with the

patient's primary symptoms. This targeted approach allows for personalized treatment adjustments and a multifaceted impact on various metabolic pathways at different stages of their function.

Clinical observations and biochemical analyses demonstrate that Cytoflavin is an effective treatment for regulating symptoms and enhancing metabolic processes. Its notable impact suggests it could be a valuable component of comprehensive care for severe neonatal asphyxia. Cytoflavin effectively addresses metabolic imbalances and acid-base disturbances, making it a promising therapeutic option in such cases.

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